

PREDICTION OF STREAM BANK FAILURE AT PATURIA FERRY GHAT OF PADMA RIVER OF BANGLADESH IN TERMS OF BANK MATERIALS

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INTRODUCTION

Bank failure phenomena are a general and most vulnerable issue in Bangladesh. The issue is intensified in those areas which are connected with highway communications and other roadways. Such a scenario has been seen in Paturia ferry ghat at Manikgonj district in Bangladesh. Banks are failed in these areas in different processes of hydraulic and geotechnical engineering. It has been created as soil types are not homogeneous at all places in the bank and river morphology is also not identical. Here a tiny attempt has been made to undertake the study to predict bank failure in terms of bank materials at Paturia ferry ghat of Padma river of Bangladesh.

METHODOLOGY

In this connection field investigation and laboratory investigation results of soils of Baruria of Paturia ferry ghat and water level and ground water level at the same are collected from the study report of River Research Institute (2020) and analyzed. The coordinates of the bore holes are BH-1(N-2633143 & E-786834) and BH-2(N-2633178 & E-786856) from where soil samples have been collected.

Figure 1: a) General soil map of Bangladesh, b) Study area map of investigation site.

As a field investigation it has been considered here some of the important soil properties. The analysis has been accomplished by means of the soil character as well as number of the hydraulic data.

Figure 2: Graph represents the surface water level (SWL) of Baruria and ground water level (GWL) of 2 stations of Shivalaya, Manikganj with time (Source: BWDB).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the analysis it has been observed that the low flood level at Paturia ferry ghat generally varies from 1.8mPWD to 2.0mPWD and high flood level varies from 7mPWD to 9mPWD. The elevation of water level at Paturia side adjacent to the bank line is 6.667mPWD to 6.935mPWD. It becomes submerge at monsoon. In this bank line, the layering of the bank material is FINE SAND mixed with some silt and trace mica. On the other hand, the stratification of the materials from the bank line to the ground surface consists of cohesive layer wherever the high flood level varies from 7mPWD to

9mPWD. This layer contains about 30% of clay particles. Due to presence of such amounts of clay particle creates a higher level of bonding among the other particles. A few numbers of the bank materials conditions have been shown in Figure 3 & 4.

Figure 3: Depth vs. particle sizes graph of the BH-1 and BH-2

Figure 4: Depth vs. permeability graph of BH-1 and BH-2

In addition it is mentioned that Padma River at Paturia ferry ghat is under pressure in all respect such as confluence of mighty Padma and Jamuna as well as communication way of mass people, road traffic, navigable traffic and passway. Therefore, waves are created by ferry and launch traffic near the bank line at Paturia ferry ghat. Terzaghi & Peck (1948) stated that the failure of a slope in a cohesive material is commonly preceded by the formation of tension cracks behind the upper edge of the slope and these soils are more resistant to surface erosion because they are less permeable. They also express that it reduces the effects of seepage, piping however, because of low permeability these soils are more susceptible to failure during rapid drawdown of water levels due to the increase in soil pore water pressures. KIMIAGHALAM et al. (2014) studied on wave-current induced erosion of cohesive riverbanks and suggested on their results that erosion rate is a function of flow and wave condition and in situ mechanical soil properties. V.K. DAS et al (2020) studied on cohesive river bank erosion mechanism under wave-current interaction and found that wave-current motion leads to an increase in shear stress at the lateral bank giving rise to erosion.

CONCLUSION

According to the study results of different authors, as wave actions and the impact of waves hitting directly on exposed soil as well as trafficking ferry and launch. So, it follows the bank failure action in addition with the remaining pore water pressures of cohesive soil. Though it has not been measured wave action parameters however, it is clear that wave action has impact on bank failure of Padma River at the Paturia ferry ghat. A design engineer may get idea about the study area's soil conditions and overall situation. For more confirmation it is recommended that further complete geotechnical and hydraulic investigation is required for bank failure of the study area.

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